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Narrowing the Gap between Christianity and Commerce through the Commercialization of Church Activities in Yenagoa, Nigeria

Abdulkadir Adewale ADAMS

*Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria*
plommedia@yahoo.com, +2348036383112,
<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1415-6473>

Abstract

The popular trend in the 21st century among religious bodies is the adoption of business practices or models in the day-to-day operation. This article seeks to examine the link between the prosperity gospel and business aspects of the Church. This research reveals how market-driven approaches affect trust relationship and congregational loyalty and faith in Church leaders who manage and control the wealth of the Church. Church leaders must therefore apply transparency mechanism in the management of Church finances and put in place governance structures that balance spiritual and business functions.

Keywords: Prosperity gospel, fund-driven approaches, religious commercialization, Church Funders, mega churches.

Introduction

The gap between the Church and business is becoming smaller as many churches have adopted business practices mainly associated with commercial entities in their day-to-day operations (Miller, 2018). This phenomenon raises fundamental questions about the integrity of the Church leaders in the

management of the wealth of the Church and the shift from traditional ecclesiastical approaches as of old where Church leaders are expected to focus on the spiritual aspects of the Church without any distraction. For example, in Acts of Apostles Chapter Six, there was a complaint against the Hebrews by the Hellenists who felt their widows were neglected in the daily distributions of food. Peter's response was that they cannot leave the word of God to serve tables.

A ministry leader once observed, "The American Church has largely become a mirror image of the capitalistic, market-driven culture we live in" (New Wine Collective, 2024). According to Fee (2006), "American Christianity is rapidly being infected by an insidious disease, the so-called "wealth and health" gospel- although it has a very little of the character of the gospel in it. People are dissatisfied with the Church because many Church founders run the Church like a business venture where making profits is the main thing. Critics argue that "mega-churches and televangelists have turned Christianity into a big business, focused more on self and fundraising than on spiritual growth and service to others" (Hinn, 2019). The emphasis on giving and prosperity rather than salvation of souls and holiness is very disturbing. Though some have argued that running a church "like a business" does not imply profit making, but rather the adoption of management practices that can enhance effectiveness and growth (Brouwer & Rose, 1996).

To what extent can the Church adopt business practices without losing focus on the kingdom mandate? What are the pit holes the Church leaders must avoid while applying business practices in the running of the Church? These are the questions and many more begging for answers. Narrowing the gap between Christianity and commerce through the commercialization of church activities is a dangerous trend that must be look into critically.

The primary aim of this research is to analyze the dangers associated with the commercialization of the Christian faith and how it affects the integrity of the Pentecostals Church. The objectives are:

- a. To compare and contrast the merits and demerits of the commercialization of the Christian faith.
- b. To evaluate the relationship between the gospel and the commercialization of the Christian faith.
- c. To make recommendation on how to adopt business practices in the running of the Church, while maintaining the spiritual standards.

This study adopts qualitative research method approach.

Literature Review

Drawing on his thirty-six years in ordained ministry, Wimberly (2010) weaves the realities of congregational dynamics and faith-centered purpose together with practical, proven approaches to business management. The relationship between the Church and commerce did not start today. However, the more recent direct adoptions of business strategies by model churches is a new phenomenon. Finke and Stark (2005) state that many churches in America adopt business strategies due to competition with other churches.

Harrison (2006) provides an engaging ethnographic account of the Word of Faith movement within African American religion, offering personal insights into prosperity theology but falling short in deeply analyzing the movement's complex relationship to African American community and progress. Bowler's "Blessed" provides the first comprehensive historical analysis of the American prosperity gospel movement, tracing its development through four central themes of faith, wealth, health, and victory, with meticulous research and balanced scholarship that illuminates the movement's origins and evolution while maintaining scholarly objectivity rather than theological critique (Oxford University Press, 2013, book description). The prosperity gospel of the contemporary American Christianity became a legitimate field of scholarly inquiry as a result of her work that bridges the gap between academic scholarship and popular religious phenomena (Bowler, 2013).

Theoretical Framework

The Religious Market Theory as developed by Rodney Stark and Roger Finke (Stark & Finke 2000) is used in this paper to explain the competition among Pentecostals churches in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. Yenagoa is the capital of Bayelsa State, the home of Ijaw people. The city is full with numerous Pentecostal churches, each competing for members through miracle and healing services, prophetic nights, deliverance programs, and social welfare initiatives. The religious market theory is relevant to understanding Yenagoa's religious landscape, especially the activities of the Pentecostal churches:

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- a. It explains the reasons why Pentecostals churches in Yenagoa compete instead of complementing each other.
 - b. The theory accounts the reason why many Pentecostals churches emphasis on giving and breakthrough rather than salvation of souls.
 - c. Competitions drive many churches to organize programs and invite “big minister” as gust preacher to attract more people to the program in order to maintain relevancy.
 - d. The theory states that churches failing to meet the demands of their members (consumers) will lose them.

Though there are limitations to the application of this theory to Yenagoa as reducing the faith of believers in God to mere marketplace transaction, however this theory provides a more robust framework for examining the various characteristics of Yenagoa’s religious landscape.

Findings

The modern churches increasingly adopt business management ethics for operational efficiency, financial and staff management, strategic planning, mobilization and organizational effectiveness (Oosthuizen, 2016). Some churches have increased their reach and effectiveness by integrating business practices and biblical principles in day-to-day operation. There is nothing wrong in applying business principles in enhancing Church growth and reach, however, the integrity and dignity of the Church must not be commercialized.

Though the Church of Christ is a spiritual entity, however, the day-to-day operation of the Church is not spiritual. The Church has different departments such as finance, administration, technical occupied by professionals (not all are born again) and that require the application of business principles for effectiveness and accountability.

Some advantages of the application of business principles in the running of the Church include:

1. ***Effective Management:*** Mega Churches grow bigger through strategic planning and diligent implementation of comprehensive budgeting processes that is follow religiously. To attract donors, the church must apply business practices that show financial transparency, stewardship, and accountability. No church grows through tithe and offering only without the financial contributions of donors and the diversification of revenue to develop other income sources. Many contemporary churches

are involved in business such as running schools, rental services, bookstores, media outlets, water factory, and real estate to create stable income sources for the ministry.

2. ***Branding and Packaging:*** The Contemporary church invests in a lot of branding and packaging because many Christians want a brand they want to belong to, not just a religious setting to attend. Church leaders know that effective branding and packaging are very essential in attracting new members to their church. Therefore, to penetrate the media space and attract new members, many churches have to invest in website design, video clips, social media, and design of attractive logo, public relation, and promotion.
3. ***Staff development and Management:*** To develop and manage the staff within the church requires the application of business practices such as regular performance evaluations, job description, succession planning, promotions, retirement remuneration, and discipline.

Some of the Demerits

1. ***Distrust:*** The push for profit-making has damaged the reputation of the Church with many leaving the faith. The public trust in the church as holy and righteous institutions is badly damaged. To a nominal Christian, the church is just another business venture in God's name. Scandals involving financial managements by church leaders are no longer strange to the public. Every Sunday, there are more people at home than in the church. In the past, communities easily allocated lands to the church without requesting for money, because they had that trust in the church. But today, since the people perceive the church as another business venture with little or no benefits for the development of the community, lands are sold to the church like any other business venture, which was not so in the past. For example, when the Catholic missionaries requested for a piece of land from the Onisha King, Obi Anazonwu in 1885 to build the first Catholic mission house, the Obi not only granted the Reverend Father's request but even allowed them possess the land on the site of their choice. They were given the legal right of ownership of the land as signed between the Holy Ghost Fathers and the King with his council (Ilega & Ngozi, 2008)
2. ***Losing interest in missions:*** The Christ Church is missions-centered, and because missions is more about giving rather than receiving,

therefore Churches that focused mainly on growth and revenue generation may lose interest in missionary engagements (Cole, 2005).

3. ***Division:*** There are hierarchies in many modern churches with the rich enjoying special privileges over the poor, as material wealth has created class distinctions among believers (Onah & Umeanolue, 2021). In fact, in some churches in Nigeria, promotion of pastors is determined by how many churches they have built. Thereby, the rich experience speedy promotion, while the poor is stagnant (Anonymous).
4. ***Exploitation of members:*** The prosperity gospel operates on the give and receive concept that has reduced faith to a transactional relationship which undermine the sacredness of spiritual walk with God. The more you give, the more you receive from God. People's faith is now monetized with the poor trying to get rich through giving, and the rich trying to sustain riches through giving. The desire of churches to generate more income may make them exclude members who are not financially buoyant from important meetings, leadership positions and decisions making.
5. ***Demonic practices in the church:*** The desire to make money through any means has pushed some ministers of the gospel to join occultist groups. Since the people will be move to give once there are signs and wonders, pastors are now desperate for powers.
6. ***Unnecessary competition:*** The more the people in the church, the more the tithe and offering, therefore, every pastor is desperate to get more members rather focusing on the spiritual needs of the members. Pastors focused on profit gradually drift away from their divine mandate toward revenue-generating activities that may have little connection to religious purposes and spiritual growth of the congregants. The Church, all around the world, is badly wounded; her members quietly departing. Unnecessary competition among pastors is very common these days.

The Prosperity Gospel and the Commercialization of the Christian faith

The prosperity gospel or word of faith is a belief system that asserts that God rewards faithfulness and devotion with material wealth and success (EBSCO Research Starters). The doctrine of prosperity is a gross example of the church's cultural accommodation to the worldly values of American materialism (McConnell, 1990). The prosperity gospel has been referred to as the "Dragon of Materialism," which leads people to become engulfed with

the material side of life (Eyre, 1987). All our time, energy and thoughts are focused in the physical aspect of life. We became practical materialists. We know that there is more to life, but the way we live shows that we adopted the creed of the Dragon of Materialism; "Matter is all that matters." (Alcorn, 2019; Eyre, 1987). This belief system sometimes makes people desperate for material success by all means. Therefore, the preachers of the prosperity gospel believe that you cannot serve God faithfully and be poor at the same time, thereby linking spiritual blessings with material success (Sarles, 1986). Therefore, the prosperity ideology creates differential treatment based on material success and justifies wealth accumulation as evidence of spiritual favor, while marginalizing those who are poor. This belief system justifies the pursuance of financial success through fundraising and business practices within the Church.

Conclusion

The Church should not be a business venture, but a spiritual entity that adopt business practices for operational effectiveness and development. The church must afford the commercialization of spiritual gifts, but focus on stewardship of God's resources for the benefit of all members. The adoption of business practices must be guided by biblical principles.

Recommendations

1. Church involvement in any business to raise extra income must be people-centered, not profit-centered. The church should only adopt business models that are void of commercial pressures, but emphasize ethical decision-making that positively affect the masses. Our Lord Jesus Christ made it very clear in the book of Matthew 21:13 that "My house shall be called a house of prayer, but you make it a den of robbers." The Church must never be view as a business venture; this will clearly contradicts the divine purpose of the Church. When money becomes the primary goal of starting a ministry, the spiritual needs of the members become secondary. Christianity is known for sacrifices and generosity, especially towards the needs in the society. The church should be the moral voice of the society, addressing social justice issues, contributing to the well-beings of the poor, and advocating for the marginalized.
2. Before any business models or practices are adopted in the day to day running of the Church, it should go through the lenses of the scriptures

that establish boundaries between worldly business patterns and godly business patterns. Business models should be a means to an end, and not an end in itself.

3. Trained believers in business practices should be allowed to run the Church business under the fatherly supervision of the Pastor in charge. Therefore, investment in leadership development programs where believers are trained and equipped with the model business techniques is essential for the sustenance of church business.
4. Further research on contemporary cross-cultural business contexts among rural missionaries is needed to enhance understanding on how local working conditions influence the adoption of business practices.
5. This research reveals how market-driven approaches affect trust relationship and congregational loyalty and faith in Church leaders who manage and control the wealth of the Church. Church leaders must therefore apply transparency mechanism in the management of Church finances and put in place governance structures that balance spiritual and business functions.

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